

AN EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON STRAIN DISTRIBUTION OF BONDED JOINT USING OPTICAL FIBER SENSOR

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1 Introduction

Bogie frame has an important role in supporting the load of the railcar body and delivering the force of traction or the braking power to a train. It consists of two side beams and two cross beams into an H-shaped frame. Side and cross beams join together with a T shaped joint as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig.1. Shape of the composite bogie frame.

Generally bonded joint, mechanical joint and hybrid joint are used to connect the composite members. Bonded joint is a simple way to use without the weight increase and the hole drilling process. At this method, bonded layer acts as a medium to transfer the load. To increase the reliability of bonded joint, strain distribution of adhesive and adherend should be measured correctly.

In this paper, strain distribution of the bonded T joint manufactured by glass/epoxy composite material was measured on a real time using the distributed optical fiber sensor. An optical fiber was attached on a 41 cm section of a T joint. Spatial resolution of the distributed fiber sensor based on the BOCDA (Brillouin optical correlation domain analysis) method was 1.5 cm.

2 Experimental procedures

2.1 Operation principle and system

The Brillouin frequency, the peak frequency of a Brillouin gain spectrum (BGS), depends on the strain and the temperature variation applied to the optical fiber. The shift of the Brillouin frequency ($\Delta\nu_B$) due to the temperature change (ΔT) and an external axial strain ($\Delta\varepsilon$) for a bare optical fiber can be expressed as follows:

$$\Delta\nu_B = C_\varepsilon \Delta\varepsilon + C_T \Delta T \quad (1)$$

where C_ε is the Brillouin strain coefficient and C_T is the Brillouin temperature coefficient [1,2].

The BOCDA is a method that generates Brillouin gain at a specified location along the optical fiber by modulating the frequency of pump wave and the counter-propagating probe wave [3]. Fig. 2 shows the schematic diagram and the configuration setup of the distributed fiber sensor system based on the BOCDA method.

(a) schematic diagram based on BOCDA method

(b) configuration of the sensor system

(c) LabView program for the real-time control of the sensor system

Fig.2. Distributed optical fiber sensor system.

The BGS was obtained by sweeping the frequency of a microwave generator from 10.3 GHz to 11.3 GHz. By changing the LD modulation frequency, a continuous distribution of the BGS along the sensing range of the optical fiber was acquired as a function of the position. The Brillouin frequency was determined by fitting the BGS with a Lorentzian curve, and its variation was converted into local strain by Eq. (1). The overall measurement process was controlled in real time by a computer algorithm coded with LabView.

2.2 Experimental setup

Specimens were manufactured with 4-harness satin fabric glass/epoxy prepregs (GEP224, SK Chem., Korea). A hollow box and a square plate to fabricate T joint were bonded using the adhesive paste (EPIKOTE™ MGS® BPR 135G, Hexion, Germany). A single mode optical fiber (Samsung, Korea) with a diameter of 250 μm was attached on the surface of the composite T joint using Araldite epoxy (Huntsman, US) with a length of 41 cm.

Fig.3. T joint specimen with a optical fiber attached on the surface.

The sensing optical fiber was connected to the distributed fiber sensor system. As shown in Fig. 4, Both end points of the T joint were fixed on supporting jigs, and a vertical load actuator (MTS, US) was placed on a jig which was 62.5 cm apart from an end point of the T joint.

Fig.4. Experimental setup to measure the strain distribution of the T joint.

3 Results

Vertical load acting on a steel beam caused the horizontal hollow box section of the T joint to bend and was increased at a rate of 0.5mm/min. The strain distribution of optical fiber was measured at every time the vertical displacement of the hollow box was increased 1mm as shown in Fig.5.

Fig.5. Strain distribution of T joint according to the vertical displacement.

At the region between two bolts on a vertical fixing jig, compressive strain was arisen (0-0.11 m position at Fig. 5). At the position of 0.11 m, a bolt to fix the square plate to a jig was located and the strain was zero. When the vertical displacement climbed up, the strain at a position of the concave adhesive fillet was positively increased (square dotted area at Fig. 5). The strain was maximized at the center of the concave adhesive fillet. Out of the adhesive fillet the strain was decreased rapidly, because a steel beam was inserted into the hollow box. To the bolted location the horizontal steel beam with the hollow box, the strain was stable and varied proportional to the vertical displacement. Finally at the concave fillet region, crack was initiated and propagated through the side section as shown in Fig. 6.

(a) initiated crack at the concave adhesive fillet

(b) location of the propagated crack in progress of the experiment

Fig.6. Crack propagation phenomenon of the T joint specimen.

The data recording speed of the fiber optic sensor system was 5Hz at each point. The spatial resolution for this measurement was 1.5 cm with 42 measurement points with 1 cm step along the optical fiber.

4 Conclusion

The strain distribution of the bonded T joint was measured using the attached optical fiber and the distributed fiber sensor system based on BOFDA method. The strain near the adhesive fillet was changed sharply and had the maximum value at the

corner. The full section of T joint was effectually monitored. The measurement of the strain distribution in this experiment can be used to verify the joint design during the vertical load test and to detect the fracture at the corner.

References

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